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A short personal recollection of Corrado Gini

Having been asked to introduce the plenary session on “Gini the demographer” in which Graziella Caselli would present the keynote paper entitled “From Gini’s approach to present-day demography: ‘tempo effects’ on demographic insights”, I have chosen to make a few short reminiscences on myself and Corrado Gini.

It was November 1, 1955, when I began my student career at Piazza Esedra in Rome university (in those days there was only “*La Sapienza*”), in the Faculty of Statistical, Demographic and Actuarial Sciences, a faculty conceived and planned by Corrado Gini. It was, incidentally, a place of extraordinary charm, particularly in the evening when one could enjoy the magnificent view from the windows of the upper floors of the beautiful and majestic fountain of the Naiads, which was lit up most suggestively. It was an extremely innovative and avant-garde faculty for the period, organized as it was in two steps, with a first two-year period at the end of which one presented a thesis and took the diploma in Statistics. Then one could continue for two more years, at the end of which another thesis was presented to gain the degree. In short, Gini had created *ante litteram* a sort of 3+2 degree course, which for every other discipline would only arrive many decades later.

The Master’s shadow hovered over every inch of the Faculty’s imposing buildings, where he had been teaching for many decades, right up to the previous day, October 31, 1955. No one mentioned this fact or commemorated it in any way. Nevertheless, there hovered over him a profound sense of respect, due to his enormous stature as a researcher, but also a profound sense of liberation, due to no longer having to submit to the tyrannical behaviour that was attributed to him, particularly by the janitors, who were not interested in him as a researcher and who described it in great detail. There was also something mysterious about him, deriving from his black attire, muffled in hat and scarf, which did not prevent him riding a bicycle from his home in Via Adige to the Faculty, even when he was no longer a member of it.

A new world began for me on that day in November 1955, with the course of Statistics 1 held by Marcello Boldrini, who was his successor in the Faculty, partly to mark some kind of break both in research and teaching. Boldrini’s course was fascinating, but treacherous when you started studying it, as the volume, though large, was not fearsomely so. It was only when you started turning its pages that you realized that they were wafer thin - India

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paper, I believe it was called - and so any progress one made in one's studies seemed physically imperceptible as day succeeded day.

The Italian Statistical Society, one of Gini's creations, was still fully in his hands, though its meetings were now somewhat under-attended. No more than five to seven people met in the Italian Reinsurance Society in Piazza San Bernardo, where its president, De Mori, who was also professor in the Faculty, played host. Nora Federici, whose assistant I had become in the meantime and whose dedication to the Master was total, "obliged" us, her pupils, to prepare a piece of research to give some minimal substance to the meetings. In 1964 I presented a paper on homogamy by place of birth in Italy, a work for which I calculated - with, a calculator that was, *de rigueur*, manual - hundreds of indices of homogamy (a measurement Gini had proposed), which clearly showed that, though the index functioned perfectly when the values of the modalities were balanced (50-50), when they were seriously unbalanced (for example, 95-5), the index became so inflexible that, in my view, it was almost useless and, therefore, unusable. And so I said in no uncertain terms that in some situations this index had serious defects. Gini, who was presiding, reacted furiously and, raising his voice, answered that what I had referred to were not defects, but characteristics, and, afterwards, Nora Federici, almost accused me of *lèse majesté*. But I was young and irresponsible, and disregarded the possibly negative consequences that the few colleagues present predicted for my career as a result of the "powers" normally attributed to his person. Not only were there no consequences, but Gini died shortly after, and, with the backing of Nora Federici and Paolo Fortunati, who became its president, I was put in charge for ten years - from 1966 to 1976 - of the Scientific Secretariat of the Italian Statistical Society which became once again a place of great intellectual vitality. We began the long, patient job of mending relations with the many who had become estranged, so that the Society and its research meetings gradually acquired momentum and vitality.

In all this, one cannot fail to feel dismayed that the terrible character of the man and the terrifying fame that surrounded his name and figure removed a scholar of such huge gifts from the Italian scientific community for so long. It is a partial consolation that, in organizing a conference on Gini for the fiftieth anniversary of his death and inviting statisticians, economists and demographers to read papers connected with subjects that were so dear to him, we have, at last, finally freed ourselves from the dark, poisonous waste materials associated with that name.